

SOCIAL BUFFERING.

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Abstract. Social buffering refers to the phenomenon where social connections and support systems act as a protective buffer against stress and adversity. It refers to the idea that having a strong social network can help individuals cope better with challenging situations and mitigate the negative impact.

Keywords. Psychology, social, human, stress, memory, mind, psyche, dominant, stressors, degrees.

In social psychology, social buffering is a phenomenon where social connections can alleviate negative consequences of stressful events. Although there are other models and theories to describe how social support can help reduce individuals' stress responses, social buffering hypothesis is one of the dominant ones. According to this idea, social partners, who can be familiar others or conspecifics, act as buffers in the face of stressful events, specifically while the stress is happening. The model further describes that social support is especially beneficial when levels of stress are also high, but buffering effects are not as relevant when levels of stress are low. Social buffering has been explored in humans and other social animals, and is important to questions about physical and mental health. Research has attempted to gain insight about the protective effects of social support in several domains, such as biological, developmental, neurological, and clinical settings. Social buffering is also relevant to other psychological processes, including fear, social bonding, and emotional reactivity. Psychological research in the mid-twentieth century began to increasingly reveal the role of stressful life events on psychological well-being. This was also around the time that there was a focus on

creating standardized approach to diagnosing mental illnesses, with the first Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Health Disorders (commonly referred to as the DSM) being published in 1952. With a honed focus on effective, universal ways to measure mental well-being, and the application of experimental psychology on social issues, a large literature on the effects of social support began to form. This occurred in an effort to fill in the gaps on the specific factors that mediate the relationship between life events and psychological consequences.

Specific focus on the attenuation of social support on the negative impacts of stressful events on physical and mental health began in the mid-1970's. This is around the time when the idea of social buffering began to take shape. It is unclear where the phrase social buffering hypothesis was first mentioned, but one of the most credited and cited works on the topic was published by researchers Sheldon Cohen and Thomas A. Wills in 1985. Social buffering has been an important feature in psychology since its early use, specifically relevant to social and health psychology. The framework has been applied to several other areas as well, and methods of measurement and definitions of relevant terminology continue to be refined and built upon. The social buffering hypothesis is often compared to or evaluated with the direct effect hypothesis.[8][19] This hypothesis differs from social buffering in that it holds that social support enhances physical and psychological well-being in general, regardless of the presence of stressors. This model says that social support is beneficial all the time, and that people with high social support have overall better health than those without it. The two models tend to deal with different measures of social support. The direct effects hypothesis measures the level at which a person is integrated into a social network, while the social buffering hypothesis assesses how available the social resources are that help people respond to stressful events. The language around both hypotheses also tends to be different, with the direct effects hypothesis often looking at the enhancement of health and well-being as a result of the perception of support and integration in a network, whereas the buffering hypothesis is more concerned with protection (or

prevention), especially in times of need. Statistically, the direct effect hypothesis holds that there is no interaction between stress and social support, meaning the same beneficial effects will be observed notwithstanding of the level of stress. Conversely, according to the social buffering hypothesis, the magnitude of the beneficial effect from social support is larger when stress is present, which is reflected in a statistically significant observable interaction when the two effects are studied experimentally. This also means that knowledge of the degree of stress is required for the social buffering hypothesis, where this level may not be as relevant in the context of the direct effects hypothesis. Despite these models providing somewhat separate explanations, research has found support for both hypotheses, and some work even suggests that both processes happen simultaneously. Researchers have suggested that work directed at critically comparing the two hypotheses may not actually benefit the field studying social support. Instead it may be more beneficial to use either as a model that aims to explain specific questions about how social support relates to mediators of health, that can be behavioral, psychological, emotional, or biological. Research studies done on social buffering and health consequences consistently show that the HPA axis plays a central role in the link between the two.

The hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis is a crucial regulator of neuroendocrine responses in the body. The HPA axis is made up of a series of pathways and feedback loops that involve the hypothalamus, anterior pituitary gland, and adrenal gland. It modulates several physiological processes, including the autonomic nervous system, immune system reactions, metabolism, and several other processes that are active during short-term physiological responses to stress. The HPA axis also plays a major role in bodily homeostasis, which includes regulating the cardiovascular system, reproductive system, and central nervous system in

¹ Thoits, Peggy A. (1982). "Conceptual, Methodological, and Theoretical Problems in Studying Social Support as a Buffer Against Life Stress". *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*.

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addition to those previously mentioned. Proper functioning of the HPA axis is very important for adaptation and development, and both over and under reactivity can lead to a series of consequences. It is important for humans to experience high levels of circulating stress hormones early in life so that they can learn to effectively respond to threat and adapt to their environments. However, too much stress in childhood can lead to long term and often irreversible dysfunction of the HPA axis. HPA axis activity goes up during aversive or arousing situations, which can be induced by physical or psychosocial events. The HPA axis is particularly sensitive to psychological stressors, including uncertainty, novelty, and the feeling of being out of control. In addition to being influenced by psychological stressors, one of the most powerful and widely studied moderators of HPA axis activity induced by stressful events is social support. This is why the HPA axis is often a focal point in physiological research examining social buffering effects.

Social support has been historically identified as very important for people's well-being, and it can be even more important for populations that are vulnerable to high stress and loneliness. Work on the social buffering hypothesis has been done on these populations, which include racial and ethnic minorities, sexual minorities, middle-aged and elderly, impoverished individuals, and other adversely affected demographic groups. This type of work aims to find specific applications of social buffering, often to provide frameworks for developing and/or assessing effectiveness of treatments or build an understanding for prevention of the negative consequences of stressful life events.

A social buffering effect was observed in work done on suicidality, and findings indicate that focusing on buffering has the potential of being an effective area in developing interventions. The buffering effect has also been found to be strong in individuals with depression, meaning that social support can reduce symptoms of depression during times of stress. A relationship has also been drawn between social buffering and drug and alcohol use disorders, which lower likelihood of developing substance abuse disorders with higher social support. Another issue

that social buffering relates to is loneliness. The United States has a growing rate of loneliness, some consider it a “loneliness epidemic”, and there is a documented rise in the number of people living alone in many cultures globally. Loneliness is strongly linked with many psychiatric disorders, including depression and anxiety, as well as several physical disorders, such as cardiovascular diseases and hypertension. Additionally, the rate of loneliness increases with age and has serious health consequences particularly in older populations. Research shows that high levels of social connectedness can help alleviate negative effects of loneliness that frequently accompany getting older. The robust connection between loneliness and poor mental and physical health is difficult to debate, and social buffering research can highlight the specific aspects of loneliness that are most damaging.

Social buffering is also relevant to the process of acculturation. Immigrants, guest workers, and international students may experience increased likelihood of isolation and psychological difficulties such as depressive symptoms. Research shows that those who have more interpersonal connections and participate in acculturation at higher degrees, benefit from the effects of social buffering. Increasing the size of one’s social network has been shown to have salient buffering effects particularly in older immigrants as well. It is important to note that social buffering works differently in different groups in society. There are gender, age, and cultural differences. Additionally, it can be difficult to study the effects of social support on stress in individuals who have impaired social functioning. These include individuals with autism spectrum disorders, social phobias, and social anxiety disorder. Social buffering is recognized as an essential way through which the nature of experiences in childhood affect development and subsequent health. During infancy, parents play a large role in regulating the negative consequences of childhood, especially regarding fear or pain responses. Attachment is also very relevant to studies on development and stress reduction. Attachment theory posits that the type of attachment relationship a child forms with their parents influences their ability to regulate emotional states whether or not the parents are immediately

present. Stress buffering effects are often seen with ²securely attached children, indicating that the type and stability of relationships is crucial to how well a child recovers from stressful events.

Nostalgia is a person's longing for a happy time or place in the past. "Nostalgia" is a combination of the Greek words "nosos" (nóstos), "homecoming" and "álgos" (álgos), "sorrow" or "sadness". 17th century fighting away from home is a Swiss term used to describe the plight of student soldiers. In modern times, melancholy is considered a medical condition, and Romanticism has become an important trope. Nostalgia is associated with longing for the past, its uniqueness, its uniqueness, especially the "good old days" or "childhood". Emotion is a powerful trigger of nostalgia. Arousing stimuli first pass through the brain's sensitized amygdala, causing nostalgia by processing such stimuli. These memories of a person's education are memories of important events, people they were interested in, and people they spent time with. Music entertainment (movies, video games, etc.) weather can also be strong triggers of nostalgia. The definition of Nostalgia has changed significantly over time. Coming from Greek roots meaning "homecoming" and "pain," homesickness has been considered a debilitating and even fatal disease for centuries. According to the modern point of view, nostalgia is an independent, positive feeling that people often experience. Nostalgia has important psychological functions, such as improving the mental state, increasing social connection, and strengthening a positive attitude to oneself. Many nostalgic memories serve more than one function and generally benefit those who experience them. Such benefits may lead to a chronic personality or personality trait called "nostalgia proneness". It is also associated with nostalgia, learning and memory enhancement. Although nostalgia is often triggered by negative emotions, nostalgic thoughts can elevate a person's mood, increase positive emotions, and cause feelings of warmth. One of the

² Lin, Nan; Woelfel, Mary W.; Light, Stephen C. (1985). "The Buffering Effect of Social Support Subsequent to an Important Life Event". *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*.

Helgeson, Vicki S. (May 1993). "Two Important Distinctions in Social Support: Kind of Support and Perceived Versus Received". *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*.

best ways to improve your mood is to effectively deal with the problems that block your happiness. Batcho (2013) found that nostalgia was positively related to successful coping methods and positive problem perception at all stages of strategy planning and implementation. These studies suggest that the coping strategies that nostalgic people may encounter are often helpful during stressful times. Nostalgia may be associated with increased support during difficult times and a greater focus on coping strategies and their implementation. Nostalgia also sometimes includes memories of people you are close to, thereby increasing a person's sense of social support and connections. Nostalgia is particularly triggered by feelings of loneliness, but is countered by the reflection of close relationships. According to Zhou (2008), lonely people often have less perception of social support. However, loneliness leads to nostalgia, which actually increases perceptions of social support. Thus, Zhou and colleagues (2008) concluded that nostalgia serves the function of restoring people's social connectedness. Nostalgia serves as a coping mechanism and helps people feel better about themselves. Vess et al. (2012) showed that subjects who thought about nostalgic memories had more positive traits than subjects who thought about future exciting experiences. Additionally, in a second study, participants in the first group experienced both nostalgic attraction and nostalgic reflection, while participants in the other group did not. The researchers again looked at their attributions and found that participants who had not been exposed to nostalgic experiences displayed a pattern of selfishness and self-centeredness. However, Vess et al. (2012), found that such characteristics were attenuated and weaker among participants who engaged in nostalgic reflection. Nostalgia can help boost self-esteem and meaning in life by buffering health fears and initiating a desire to deal with problems or stress. Routledge (2011) and colleagues found that nostalgia is positively related to a person's sense of meaning in life. A second study found that nostalgia increases a person's sense of meaning in life, which is thought to be related to feelings of social support and connectedness. Third, researchers have found that even the underlying meaning of fear can always serve as a trigger for nostalgia, which increases nostalgic

reflection. By triggering nostalgia, as shown in the fourth study, a person's ability to defend against such fears is minimized. Two recent studies have shown that nostalgia can not only create meaning, but also buffer fears by disrupting the link between meaninglessness and human well-being. An observational study completed by Routledge in 2012 not only found meaning as a function of nostalgia, but also concluded that nostalgic people have greater perceptual meaning, search less for meaning, and are better able to buffer existential dread. A recent study criticizes the idea that nostalgia, in some forms, can become a defense mechanism for people to avoid historical facts. This study examines the different representations of apartheid in South Africa and suggests that nostalgia manifests itself in two ways: "restorative nostalgia", the desire to return to that past, and the more critical "reflective nostalgia". Reliving past memories can provide comfort and contribute to mental health. A recent medical study looked at the physiological effects of thinking about "good" memories from the past. They found that thinking about the past "fondly" actually increased feelings of physical warmth. In a 2014 Routledge study, he and a group observed that the more people think about major changes and uncertainties in their lives, the more they miss the past. Routledge suggests that by using the idea of an idealized past, politicians can use nostalgia as a tool of political persuasion to make social appeals that appeal to cultural anxieties and uncertainties.

This term was introduced in 1688 by Johannes Hofer (1669-1752) in his Basel thesis. Hofer included nostalgia as "homesickness" and also *mal du Suisse* as "Swiss disease" due to the fact that Swiss mercenaries frequented the beautiful nature of their homeland on the Swiss plains. Symptoms of this disease include fainting, high fever and death. Sir Joseph Banks used the term in his journal during Captain Cook's first voyage, but the journal was not published during his lifetime. Soldiers were sometimes released in cases of death and recovered when sent home. However, receiving the diagnosis was generally considered an insult to the soldier.

By the 1850s, nostalgia had lost its status as a specific disease and was seen more as a symptom or stage of a pathological process. It was considered a form of

melancholia and a suicidal state. However, nostalgia was still diagnosed among soldiers during the American Civil War. By the 1870s, interest in nostalgia as a medical category had largely faded. Nostalgia was still recognized during the First and Second World Wars, especially by the American armed forces. A lot of time was spent on researching and understanding the reason for stopping the flow of troops leaving the front in droves (see the BBC documentary *The Age of Self*).

Nostalgia is triggered by memories of past events. The resulting emotions can vary from happiness to sadness. The term "nostalgia" is commonly used to describe the pleasant feelings associated with longing to return to a certain time period. In media and advertising, nostalgic images, sounds, and references can be used strategically to create a sense of connection between consumers and products to persuade the public to consume, view, or purchase advertised products. Modern technology prepares nostalgia through advertising theme, style and design. Nostalgia is easily communicated through social media and advertising, as these media are multi-emotional, fully expressive, and therefore more reminiscent of past lives. Effective advertising schemes do not require consumers to experience a specific event or time in order to experience nostalgia. This is due to a phenomenon called representative nostalgia. Representative nostalgia is a feeling of longing for a moment that occurred before or outside the memory, but is associated (and has sentimental value) with the result of repeated exposure to it. The constant promotion of advertising and other media creates nostalgia.

Forestalgia, characterized as an idealized person's desire for the future developed within the framework of marketing, serves as the future-oriented counterpart of nostalgia. Like nostalgia, where only happy memories remain, forestalgia explains people's desire to escape from the present, a romanticized future that favors present concerns. Marketing researchers have found that long-past nostalgia and long-future forestalgia are the most effective ways to promote and promote hedonic and utilitarian products. In contrast, advertising with nostalgia for

the distant past or forestalgia of the near future was more appropriate for entertainment products.

Some research shows that parents are especially important for social buffering up until around puberty or late childhood, when primary caregivers tend to become less influential than peers in social settings. This does not take away from the role that parents play in social buffering as a whole, and instead reflects how they are replaced by friends who become a major source of social support with buffering. Furthermore, major stressors during adolescence and puberty tend to be peers and social standing, so the social buffering provided by friends during this time is heavily interwoven with social networks and relates to an idea called the friendship protection hypothesis. The friendship protection hypothesis reflects the idea of the social buffering hypothesis and explains how children with at least one supportive friend are less negatively affected by bullying and peer rejection. When looking at social buffering and development, a common approach to measuring stress responses involves looking at the HPA axis. The HPA axis is referred to as one of the primary hormonal stress systems. Research looking at stress and social buffering in development consistently shows that parents play a role in shaping HPA axis function, which is evidenced in part by how early social deprivation may later result in long term dysfunction of stress reactivity. Social buffering effects have also been observed when a child is exposed to a threatening event. The presence of a parent during such a time can lower or completely block the activation of the HPA axis. Additional support for the social buffering hypothesis and social neuroscience involves fear conditioning. The amygdala has been recognized as an important part in the process of fear learning, and research has shown that children have reduced amygdala activity when around a parent. In addition to this, greater connectivity between the prefrontal cortex and amygdala was observed when a child viewed their mother compared to a stranger. The prefrontal cortex is involved in emotional processes so communication between the two brain areas indicates that parents play a large role in emotional regulation and provide neurological support for social

buffering. Although the functioning of stress processes and fear learning are evolutionarily crucial, research on social buffering shows that social support can reduce the negative developmental consequences of too high stress and potentially aid with proper biological functioning.

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